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Executive summary

The Region of Western Macedonia in Greece represents one of Europe's most emblematic cases of transition-related vulnerability. For nearly seventy years the region functioned as the **primary energy hub of Greece**, hosting approximately 80% of national lignite mining capacity and contributing between 34% and 45% of regional gross value added at its peak. The Greek government's 2019 commitment to a complete **lignite phase-out by 2028** has set in motion a profound socio-economic reconfiguration, unfolding against deep structural constraints: population declined by 10.3% between 2011 and 2021, lifelong learning participation stands at just 3–4%, and the region is classified as an "Emerging Innovator" under the Regional Innovation Scoreboard. The policy response is anchored in the Just Transition Development Plan (JTDP), supported by the Just Transition Fund, the Recovery and Resilience Facility, ESF+, and ERDF, and complemented by the SYNERGiNN European Digital Innovation Hub for SME digitalisation.

This case study examines how policies supporting the twin green and digital transition interact with existing socio-economic inequalities, with a focus on employment dynamics, skills development, and access to emerging opportunities. The analysis demonstrates that the transition is shaped by deeply embedded inequalities across the policy cycle. Large-scale renewable energy investments generate lower employment intensity than the lignite sector and have limited local economic spillovers. Up to 50% of affected workers require reskilling, yet training programmes delivered through the Public Employment Service (DYPA) are not consistently aligned with actual labour demand. Access to funding is conditioned by administrative complexity — described by local stakeholders as a "technical race" — that systematically advantages institutionally stronger actors, while spatial concentration of investment and energy poverty risks from the disruption of lignite-based district heating further compound these dynamics.

Without recalibration, the transition risks replacing a carbon-intensive monoculture with a more technologically advanced but equally exclusionary development model. The study calls for stronger place-based governance, demand-driven reskilling aligned with actual job openings, simplified funding access for SMEs and local actors, integrated energy poverty support measures, and expanded monitoring frameworks capable of capturing who benefits from the transition and under what conditions.

1 Introduction

1.1. Background and context: a carbon-dependent region in transition

The European Union has positioned the twin transition - the simultaneous shift towards a climate-neutral and digitally advanced economy - at the core of its long-term strategy for sustainable growth, competitiveness, and territorial cohesion (European Commission, 2020). While the green and digital transitions are expected to be mutually reinforcing, enabling new technological pathways and productivity gains, a growing body of literature highlights that they may also reproduce or exacerbate existing socio-economic inequalities if not carefully designed and implemented (Carley and Konisky, 2020, OECD 2023). These risks are particularly pronounced in carbon-intensive regions, where economic structures, labour markets, and social systems have historically been organised around fossil-fuel-based industries.

Within this broader European context, the **Region of Western Macedonia in Greece represents one of the most emblematic cases** of transition-related vulnerability. For decades, the region has been deeply embedded in a lignite-based development model, generating strong economic, institutional, and technological path dependencies that now constrain its capacity to adapt to the twin transition (Ziouzios et al., 2021, Lypiridi, 2021). Western Macedonia functioned for nearly seventy years as the primary energy hub of Greece, hosting approximately 80% of national lignite mining and electricity generation capacity (Hellenic Ministry of Environment and Energy, 2021). At its peak in the early 2000s, lignite production reached approximately 55.8 million tons annually, supporting a substantial share of regional employment and contributing between 34% and 45% of regional gross value added (European Commission, 2020, IEA, 2021).

This prolonged reliance on a single industrial sector resulted in a structurally undiversified regional economy, limited innovation spillovers, and significant environmental degradation. As external pressures intensified (particularly through rising carbon prices under the EU Emissions Trading System, increasing competition from renewable energy sources, and the ageing of lignite infrastructure) the viability of this model progressively weakened (European Commission, 2020, Kollatou et al., 2025). **The turning point came in 2019, when the Greek government announced an accelerated lignite phase-out strategy aligned with the European Green Deal.** While this decision marked a decisive shift towards decarbonisation, it simultaneously introduced substantial socio-economic risks, especially for regions structurally dependent on fossil fuels.

BOX 1 The Lignite Phase-out Landscape in Western Macedonia

Western Macedonia has historically been the centre of Greece's lignite-based energy system. In 2019, the Greek government announced an accelerated decarbonisation strategy, committing to the closure of most lignite-fired power plants by 2023 and a complete phase-out by 2028 (European Commission, 2022, Lypiridi, 2021).

The global energy crisis of 2022 led to temporary adjustments to this timeline. Selected lignite units were allowed to operate until 2025 to ensure energy security, while the newly constructed Ptolemaida V plant is expected to operate on lignite until 2028 before transitioning to lower-emission fuels (Hellenic Ministry of Environment and Energy, 2022).

Despite these adjustments, the strategic direction of decarbonisation remains unchanged. The transition is expected to have substantial socio-economic implications, including employment losses affecting up to 16,000 jobs directly and indirectly, as well as broader impacts on regional economic stability (Christiaensen and Ferré, 2020, European Commission, 2022).

What distinguishes Western Macedonia from many other European transition regions is not only the depth of its dependence on a single carbon-intensive sector, but also the **speed and compression of the transition timeline**. The accelerated phase-out intensifies the scale and urgency of economic restructuring, placing considerable pressure on local labour markets, institutions, and governance systems. In this sense, the transition constitutes not only an environmental and technological transformation but also a **profound socio-economic reconfiguration** that effectively tests the capacity of the European Union's Just Transition Mechanism (JTM) to deliver territorially balanced outcomes.

Figure 1 Withdrawal schedule of the installed lignite power by 2028; Source: Public Power Corporation of Greece, JTDP

1.2 The twin transition landscape: structural transformation under constraints

Building on this context, the twin transition in Western Macedonia can be understood as a systemic shift from a centralised, carbon-intensive industrial model to a more diversified and digitally enabled economic structure. However, this transformation does not unfold on a neutral ground. It is embedded in a regional context characterised by demographic decline, labour market imbalances, and limited innovation capacity-conditions that shape both the trajectory and the inclusiveness of the transition.

Demographic trends illustrate these constraints clearly. The **region's population declined** by approximately 10.3% between 2011 and 2021, largely driven by youth out-migration (ELSTAT, 2022). At the same time, participation in lifelong learning remains particularly low, estimated at around 3–4%, significantly below the EU average (Eurostat, 2023). These structural characteristics reduce the adaptive capacity of the regional economy and increase the likelihood that certain groups will be excluded from emerging opportunities.

Within this constrained environment, the green transition is primarily driven by the phase-out of lignite-based energy production and the expansion of renewable energy infrastructure. Supported by the Just Transition Fund and national development strategies, investments focus on large-scale photovoltaic and wind energy projects, environmental rehabilitation of former mining areas, and the development of circular economy activities (European Commission, 2022, Kollatou et al., 2025). At the same time, the restructuring of district heating systems-through biomass and alternative energy sources-aims to maintain energy provision while mitigating emerging risks of energy poverty (Andreosatou, 2024).

The digital transition is closely intertwined with these developments, as it is expected to play a central role in economic diversification and job creation. Given the lower labour intensity of renewable energy systems compared to lignite-based industries, digitalisation becomes a key mechanism for generating new economic activity. Initiatives such as the European Digital Innovation Hub “SYNERGiNN” seek to support this process by enhancing the digital capabilities of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and public organisations, focusing on technologies such as artificial intelligence, the Internet of Things, cybersecurity, and data analytics (SYNERGiNN EDIH, 2024).

1.3 The transition challenge: inequalities at the core of transformation

Against this backdrop, the transition in Western Macedonia is not merely a technological and economic restructuring process, but a deeply social and spatial transformation shaped by pre-existing inequalities. These inequalities influence both the capacity of actors to participate in the transition and the distribution of its costs and benefits.

From a **labour market perspective**, the region faces significant risks of structural unemployment due to the mismatch between the skills of former lignite workers and the requirements of emerging sectors (Christiaensen and Ferré, 2020, SEED CoVEs, 2023). The

decline of relatively well-paid industrial employment is likely to generate downward pressure on wages and increase labour market segmentation.

Figure 2 Monthly unemployment fluctuations in the Region of Western Macedonia with an analysis of long-term (orange line) and short-term (blue line) unemployment; Source: Public Employment Service DYPA

These labour dynamics are closely linked to **spatial inequalities**. Investments in renewable energy and digital innovation tend to concentrate in specific locations - primarily urban centres - while rural and peripheral areas face more limited access to new opportunities. This uneven spatial distribution raises concerns related to spatial justice and territorial cohesion (Soja, 2010).

At the same time, **social inequalities** related to gender, age, and income are likely to intensify during the transition. Emerging evidence points to increased risks of energy poverty, particularly among households previously dependent on lignite-based district heating systems, as well as unequal access to training and employment opportunities (Andreosatou, 2024, Stergiou et al., 2024).

Importantly, these inequalities are not simply outcomes of the transition. They actively shape how policies are designed, implemented, and experienced across different groups and territories. Understanding these dynamics is therefore central to assessing the effectiveness of transition policies.

1.4 Rationale and justification of case selection

The relevance of Western Macedonia as a case study becomes clearer when situated within the broader national and European context. According to the Eco-Innovation Index (2024), Greece performs at approximately 71.3% of the EU average, reflecting moderate progress but persistent structural weaknesses in areas such as environmental R&D investment and eco-innovation outputs (European Commission, 2024). Similarly, the Transition Performance Index classifies Greece as a “catching-up performer” in economic transition, highlighting

challenges in structural transformation and diversification. In terms of digitalisation, Greece consistently ranks below the EU average in the Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI), particularly with regard to the integration of digital technologies in businesses (European Commission, 2023). At the regional level, Western Macedonia is classified as an “Emerging Innovator”, indicating limited innovation capacity and technological specialisation.

Against this background, Western Macedonia provides a particularly relevant case for examining how transition policies interact with existing inequalities. Its combination of strong fossil-fuel dependence and limited innovation capacity allows for a clear observation of how policy interventions shape distributional outcomes in the context of the twin transition.

1.5 Scope of the study and methodological approach

This study examines how policies supporting the twin transition in Western Macedonia interact with existing socio-economic inequalities, with a particular focus on employment dynamics, skills development, and access to emerging economic opportunities. The central policy problem addressed is the misalignment between the rapid implementation of decarbonisation targets and the absorptive capacity of the regional economy, labour market, and institutional system.

The analysis focuses on the operationalisation of key policy instruments, rather than only their strategic objectives. In particular, it examines:

- (i) labour market interventions implemented through ESF+ funding, including training voucher schemes delivered by the Public Employment Service (DYPA),
- (ii) digital innovation support mechanisms provided by the SYNERGiNN European Digital Innovation Hub (EDIH), such as digital maturity assessments, “test-before-invest” services, and firm-level training in advanced technologies, and
- (iii) investment-led interventions under the Just Transition Development Plan (JTDP), particularly large-scale renewable energy projects and associated economic diversification measures.

By focusing on these concrete mechanisms, the study analyses how policy design translates into actual participation conditions for different actors - workers, firms, and local institutions- and how these conditions shape access to transition-related opportunities.

The analysis addresses a set of interconnected challenges, including structural unemployment linked to skill mismatches, uneven participation in training and innovation programmes, spatial disparities in access to investment, and emerging vulnerabilities such as energy poverty and demographic decline (Andreosatou, 2024, Stergiou et al., 2024).

Methodologically, the study combines policy document analysis at European and national levels with quantitative data from Eurostat and national statistical sources. These are complemented by qualitative insights derived from stakeholder interviews conducted in 2025 with regional and national actors involved in the transition. The analytical framework is informed by a Theory of Change perspective, which enables the systematic examination of

the relationship between policy assumptions, implementation mechanisms, and observed outcomes. This approach supports the identification of the pathways through which policies influence inequality dynamics and provides a basis for assessing their effectiveness in promoting more inclusive transition processes.

2 Twin transition policy process: governance, policy mix and implementation

The twin transition in Western Macedonia is governed through a multi-level policy architecture that combines European strategic frameworks, national policy priorities, and regional implementation mechanisms. This architecture seeks to coordinate decarbonisation, economic restructuring, and digital transformation within a coherent policy mix. At the same time, the interaction between governance levels plays a central role in shaping how policy objectives are translated into practice and how the outcomes of the transition are distributed across actors and territories.

Rather than unfolding as a linear policy cycle, the transition can be understood as a layered process, where decisions taken at European and national levels are implemented within regional socio-economic contexts characterised by specific structural constraints and institutional capacities.

2.1 Governance architecture and actor dynamics

The governance of the transition combines central strategic coordination with a broad ecosystem of actors involved in implementation. At the national level, the Ministry of Environment and Energy and the Managing Authority of the Just Transition Development Plan (EYDAM) define priorities, allocate resources, and oversee implementation. European institutions shape the overall framework through funding instruments such as the Just Transition Mechanism (JTM) and the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF), as well as through regulatory commitments associated with the European Green Deal.

At the regional level, the Region of Western Macedonia and local municipalities are responsible for programme implementation, local economic adjustment, and the management of transition-related impacts. Additional roles are played by the Public Power Corporation (PPC), intermediary organisations such as ANKO, digital support structures such as the SYNERGiNN EDIH, research institutions including the University of Western Macedonia and CERTH, as well as SMEs and civil society actors.

Within this configuration, differences in decision-making authority, administrative capacity, and access to financial and technical resources are observable across actors. Strategic direction is largely determined at the national level, while regional and local actors operate within established frameworks. These differences influence the extent to which actors are able to design projects, access funding instruments, and participate in implementation processes.

Participation in the transition is therefore differentiated. Actors with higher levels of administrative capacity, technical expertise, and financial resources—such as large firms, external investors, and experienced institutions—are generally better positioned to engage with policy instruments. Other actors, including smaller municipalities, local SMEs, and civil

society organisations, often engage under more constrained conditions, particularly where access to specialised knowledge or support services is required.

Stakeholder consultation processes have been incorporated into transition planning. Available evidence indicates variation in the extent to which these processes influence final policy decisions. This variation is reflected in differences between national-level policy framing-emphasising modernisation and opportunity-and regional-level perspectives, which more frequently highlight adjustment challenges and socio-economic implications (Spanidis et al., 2025).

Table 1 Mainstakeholders and their roles

Sector	Stakeholders	Role
Public Sector (European/ National)	European Commission	Defines overarching climate and digital policy frameworks (European Green Deal, Digital Decade); provides financial support through the Just Transition Mechanism (JTM) and the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF); ensures regulatory oversight
	Ministry of Environment and Energy	Leads national decarbonisation strategy through the National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP) and the Just Transition Development Plan; defines transition timelines and sectoral priorities
	Managing Authority of the JTDP (EYDAM)	Responsible for the design, coordination, and monitoring of Just Transition policies; operationalises Territorial Just Transition Plans.
	Ministry of Finance	Manages allocation of RRF funds
	Ministry of Labour and Social Security	Aligns labour market and social policies, including skills strategies and employment support mechanisms
	Public Employment Service (DYPA)	Implementing body for labour market interventions, delivers ESF+ training voucher schemes and the "50,000 unemployed" programme under Greece 2.0 to reskill displaced lignite workers, while also serving as the primary source of regional unemployment data, including short/long-term unemployment trends and educational profiles of jobseekers.
Public Sector (Regional & Local)	Regional Authority of Western Macedonia	Integrates transition objectives into regional development strategies; manages regional programmes (ERDF/ESF+); supports implementation of RIS3
	Managing authority of the Just Transition Development Plan (JTDP)	Leads the central design and programming of just transition policies, coordinates the implementation of Territorial Just Transition Plans, monitors the progress of projects / actions implemented under the JTDP
	Managing authority of the Programme <i>Western Macedonia 2021–2027</i>	Designs the programme priorities and ensures alignment with EU cohesion policy, national strategies, and regional needs.

Sector	Stakeholders	Role
		Integrates green and digital transition objectives into regional development planning.
	Local Municipalities (Kozani, Florina, Amindeo)	Implement local interventions, including district heating transition and local economic adjustment; manage immediate socio-economic impacts of mine closures.
Public-Private and Intermediary Bodies	Regional Development Agency of Western Macedonia (ANKO S.A.)	Supports implementation of the Just Transition Development Plan; provides technical assistance, SME support, and innovation ecosystem development
	SYNERGiNN EDIH	Provides digital transformation services (“test before invest”), digital maturity assessments, and training in AI, IoT, cybersecurity for SMEs and public actors.
Private Sector	Public Power Corporation (PPC S.A.)	Manages lignite phase-out, decommissioning, and land rehabilitation; invests in large-scale renewable energy infrastructure.
	Technology and clean-tech providers	Deploy digital and energy technologies (smart grids, storage, RES); often multinational actors with strong technical capacity.
	Local SMEs and start-ups	Target group for diversification; face constraints in accessing finance, skills, and innovation support.
	Chamber of Commerce and Industry	Supports local businesses, trade unions and labour representatives
Citizen associations and civil society groups	NGOs and youth organisations	Promote participation, policy critique, and inclusion; advocate for energy democracy and youth engagement (The Green Tank, 2021; Stergiou et al., 2024).
Educational Sector	University of Western Macedonia	Hosts Just Transition Observatory and contributes to skills development, research, and regional innovation.
	University of Western Macedonia/ Just Transition Observatory (JT-Observatory)	Monitors the social, economic, and environmental aspects of the transition

2.2 Policy orientation and design: strategic priorities and structural conditions

The policy framework guiding the transition reflects the interaction between European climate commitments, national strategic priorities, and regional development objectives. The accelerated lignite phase-out announced in 2019 established a defined pathway for decarbonisation, while also setting a relatively compressed timeframe for economic restructuring at the regional level.

This orientation is closely linked to broader European policy instruments that provide both strategic direction and financial resources. In particular, the Just Transition Mechanism (JTM) under Cohesion Policy, the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF), and the Digital Europe

Programme shape the structure of interventions by linking decarbonisation objectives with economic diversification and digitalisation priorities. These frameworks introduce specific conditionalities-such as climate targets, investment timelines, and digital adoption benchmarks-which influence both the scope of policy design and the types of projects prioritised at the regional level.

The **Just Transition Development Plan (JTDP)** constitutes the central policy framework, structured around five pillars: clean energy, industry and trade, sustainable agriculture, tourism, and research and innovation. Digital initiatives-particularly through the **SYNERGIINN European Digital Innovation Hub**-complement this framework by supporting technological upgrading and diversification across sectors.

The design of the policy mix combines environmental, economic, and social objectives. At the same time, it places significant emphasis on large-scale investment projects, particularly in renewable energy and infrastructure. These investments are expected to contribute to economic restructuring and the achievement of climate targets. Their scale and technical requirements, however, are associated with specific participation conditions, including access to capital, technical expertise, and project development capacity.

While the overall policy orientation is shaped by European and national drivers - including climate targets, carbon pricing mechanisms, and energy strategies - regional socio-economic conditions have been incorporated more gradually into the policy framework. Structural characteristics such as labour market composition, demographic trends, and institutional capacity continue to influence how policies operate in practice.

This **interaction between strategic priorities and structural conditions** is central to understanding how policy design translates into differentiated patterns of access and participation.

In practice, these participation conditions translate into **differentiated access to policy instruments**. For example, large-scale renewable energy investments typically require complex licensing procedures, upfront capital, and technical project development capacity, which are more readily available to large firms and external investors. Similarly, access to innovation and digitalisation support often presupposes a minimum level of organisational readiness and prior engagement with funding mechanisms, which not all local actors possess.

2.3 Implementation dynamics: labour market adjustment, skills and absorptive capacity

As the transition moves into implementation, the interaction between policy instruments and regional structures becomes more pronounced. The phase-out of lignite is associated with substantial employment adjustments, with estimates indicating that approximately 10,000 to 16,000 jobs may be affected directly and indirectly.

New employment opportunities are expected to emerge, particularly in renewable energy, construction, land rehabilitation, and related sectors. These opportunities, however, differ in terms of duration and skill requirements. Construction and infrastructure activities are

associated with short- to medium-term employment and may utilise skills partially transferable from the lignite sector. In contrast, longer-term employment in emerging sectors - such as advanced energy systems, digital technologies, and research-intensive activities - requires more specialised qualifications.

This differentiation creates a **structural adjustment challenge**. A significant proportion of the workforce does not currently possess the skills required for emerging roles. Estimates suggest that up to 50% of affected workers may require reskilling, particularly in relation to digital competencies and technical specialisation. At the same time, participation in lifelong learning remains relatively low (approximately 3 - 4%), which may influence the pace and scope of workforce adaptation.

W. Macedonia: ~2,600 positions (~47%) are expected to require moderate or high reskilling

Initial assessment

New skills	Positions to cover	Absorbed skills and coverage ¹	Difference	Reskilling need
Architects, engineers	~215	Engineers / Physicists (~1,130)	+915	●
Craftsmen, drivers, etc. ¹	~1,295	Drivers / Operators (~1,450)	+155	●
Doctors, nurses, etc. ³	~220	Biologists / Doctors (~420)	+200	●
Business Executives	~515	Economists (~210) Office Workers (~1,130)	-825	●
Researchers, scientists	~615	Engineers / Physicists (~915)	+300	●
Horticulturists, agronomists, winemakers	~160	General Duties (~450)	+290	●
Farmers, stockbreeders	~260	Unskilled workers (~1,220)	+960	●
Catering tourism professionals	~520	Merchant / Sellers (~1,800)	+1,280	●
Other administrative staff	~1,615	Office Workers (~820) Merchants/Salesmen (~1,280)	+485	●
Total	~5,415	~7,850	+2,400	

● Low (<1 month intra-corporate) ● Moderate (1-3 months in a competent body) ● High (3+ months in a competent body)

Note: Skills marked with 'bold' are absorbed into two skills for this and displayed with different numbers in parentheses. Were the Indirect and Induced Jobs estimated based on the multipliers of TEE w. Macedonia? 1. In parentheses the number of positions that can be filled per skill. 2. Secondary absorption option. Source: SDAM Group Analysis

Figure 3 Skills gap in Western Macedonia; Source: Just Development Transition Plan (SDAM) employment impact assessment

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Existing work skills determine the potential for absorption of existing human resources

Ability to absorb new skills

Initial assessment

Existing skills		Engineers etc.	Craftsmen etc.	Horticulturists etc.	Farmers etc.	Researchers etc.	Catering professionals	Executives etc.	Administrative staff	Doctors etc.
Traders / sellers	~1,800									
Drivers / operators	~1,450									
Unskilled workers	~1,220									
Office workers	~1,130									
Engineers / physicists etc.	~1,130									
Construction technicians	~660									
General duties	~450									
Biologists / doctors etc.	~420									
Teachers	~240									
Economists	~210									
Others	~890									
Available Human Resour.	~9,400									
Positions to cover		~215	~1,295	~160	~260	~615	~515	~520	~1,615	~220

■ Primary absorption option
 ■ Secondary absorption option
 ■ Non relevant exp.

Other administrative staff? Source: SDAM Team Analysis | Absorption option based on professional experience.

Figure 4 Estimated capacity of the existing workforce in Western Macedonia; Source: Just Development Transition Plan (SDAM) employment impact assessment

Skills policies have been introduced to address these gaps. Their effectiveness depends on the extent to which training provision is aligned with labour market demand and with ongoing investment projects. Evidence from policy evaluations and stakeholder consultations indicates that such alignment varies, with implications for the translation of training into employment outcomes.

The **implementation of digital policies** is similarly shaped by the characteristics of the regional economy. Initiatives such as the SYNERGiNN EDIH provide access to advanced technologies and advisory services. However, many SMEs face constraints related to financial resources, organisational capacity, and access to specialised expertise. Participation in funding programmes is also associated with administrative requirements that may affect different actors unevenly. In practical terms, these requirements are often described by local stakeholders as a **“technical race” for accessing funding**, where successful participation depends on the ability to prepare technically complex proposals, navigate bureaucratic procedures, and mobilise co-financing. Smaller firms and local actors frequently rely on external consultants to meet these requirements, which introduces additional costs and uncertainty.

These factors contribute to differentiated patterns of engagement with policy instruments. Actors with greater capacity to mobilise resources and navigate institutional processes tend to participate more intensively, while others engage more gradually or selectively.

2.4 Monitoring, Evaluation and the Visibility of Distributional Outcomes

Monitoring of the transition is supported by institutional mechanisms such as the **Just Transition Observatory**, which tracks progress across economic, social, and environmental

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dimensions. This framework provides a structured basis for assessing implementation and supports the development of evidence-based policy.

Current monitoring practices **focus primarily on inputs and outputs**, including funding allocation, number of projects, and participation in programmes. These indicators provide important insights into implementation dynamics. At the same time, there is more limited systematic tracking of distributional outcomes, such as employment quality, income changes, and access to opportunities across different social groups and territories.

Figure 5 JT Data Mechanism; Source: National Observatory for Just Development Transition (2023), Indicator System and Digital Monitoring Platform.

The scope of monitoring influences the type of information available for policy adjustment. Where distributional dimensions are less visible, the interaction between policy interventions and existing inequalities may be only partially captured. Expanding the range of indicators to include such dimensions could support a more comprehensive understanding of transition outcomes and inform future policy refinement.

Figure 6 Observatory's data support research, studies, and European indicators; Source: <https://eydam.gr/en/ethniko-paratiritirio-dikaiis-anaptyxiakis-metavasis>.

2.5 Synthesis: policy process and differentiated outcomes

The analysis indicates that the outcomes of the twin transition in Western Macedonia are shaped by the interaction between **governance arrangements, policy design choices, and regional socio-economic conditions**.

Differences in decision-making authority and administrative capacity influence how policies are implemented across actors and territories. The emphasis on large-scale investments interacts with local economic structures and capabilities, shaping participation patterns. The effectiveness of skills and innovation policies depends on their alignment with labour market demand and the absorptive capacity of regional actors. Finally, the current monitoring framework provides partial visibility of distributional effects.

These dynamics suggest that the **transition operates through differentiated pathways, reflecting variations in access, capability, and institutional positioning**. The following chapter builds on this analysis by examining more directly the mechanisms through which these dynamics translate into patterns of inequality.

3 Policy Analysis

3.1 Analytical framework: policy assumptions, mechanisms and inequality dynamics

The twin transition in Western Macedonia is structured around a central policy assumption: that large-scale investments in renewable energy infrastructure, combined with targeted support for digital innovation and skills development, can progressively substitute the socio-economic role historically performed by lignite-based activities. This assumption underpins the policy mix implemented through the Just Transition Development Plan (JTDP), the Just Transition Mechanism (JTM), and complementary European and national instruments.

At the same time, transitions operate within pre-existing socio-economic structures that shape how policy interventions unfold. As highlighted in the literature on energy justice and spatial inequality, the effects of transition policies are mediated by differences in economic structure, institutional capacity, and access to resources (Carley and Konisky, 2020; Soja, 2010). In Western Macedonia, these conditions include a high degree of economic mono-specialisation, labour market rigidities, and asymmetries in governance capacity.

The analysis distinguishes between policy assumptions, intervention mechanisms, and distributional outcomes. This approach allows for a systematic examination of how inequalities are shaped across the policy process, and how the interaction between green and digital policies contributes to these dynamics.

3.2 Structural Drivers of Inequalities

Table 2 Drivers

Drivers	Subcategory	Definition
Economic dynamics	Single-sector dependence on lignite	Long-term dependence on lignite-based activities created a highly specialised regional economy with limited diversification. The rapid phase-out generates a large-scale structural adjustment, affecting an estimated 15,000–20,000 jobs and constraining the capacity of the local economy to absorb displaced labour.
	Labour-market mismatch and unequal reskilling capacity	Workers displaced from carbon-intensive sectors often lack the digital and technical skills required in emerging green and digital jobs. Low participation in lifelong learning (around 3–4%) and educational structure (majority with secondary or lower education) influence the ability to benefit from reskilling programmes such as ESF+ training vouchers.
	Financial and investment structures	The transition is characterised by capital-intensive renewable energy investments, often implemented by large firms. These investments generate lower long-term employment and may

Drivers	Subcategory	Definition
		rely on external supply chains, influencing the distribution of economic benefits and limiting local spillovers.
Societal change	Demographic decline and brain drain	Population decline (over 10% between 2011–2021) and youth out-migration reduce the availability of skilled labour and weaken regional innovation capacity, affecting the sustainability of new economic activities.
	Uneven social perceptions and participation	Differences in exposure to transition-related investments shape local perceptions. Areas with limited visible benefits tend to express more negative expectations, influencing participation and acceptance of transition policies.
Technology developments	Emerging skill requirements and occupational restructuring	The twin transition introduces new occupational profiles combining technical and digital skills (e.g. in renewable energy systems, digital services, AI applications). This increases the complexity of labour market transitions and raises entry barriers for workers lacking either skill set.
	Digital divide and connectivity constraints	Access to digital infrastructure and digital literacy conditions participation in training and innovation programmes. Limited digital skills among older workers and gaps in connectivity affect access to online platforms and services.
	Firm-level absorptive capacity	Firms with higher organisational capacity, financial resources, and prior technological experience are more likely to adopt digital solutions (e.g. through SYNERGiNN EDIH services), while micro-enterprises and traditional firms face constraints in engaging with these processes.
Institutional capacities	Uneven administrative and governance capacity	Differences in administrative capacity across actors influence the ability to design projects, access funding, and implement interventions. Complex procedures create differentiated participation conditions, often described as a “technical race” for accessing funding.
	Spatial concentration of innovation and support structures	The location of training centres, digital hubs, and innovation infrastructure influences access to support services, with peripheral areas facing more limited opportunities for participation in reskilling and innovation programmes.
Regulatory framework	Binding transition targets and timelines	National and European policy frameworks (e.g. NECP 2021–2030, European Green Deal) establish binding decarbonisation targets, including the phase-out of lignite by 2028. These

Drivers	Subcategory	Definition
		commitments define the pace of transition and constrain policy flexibility at the regional level.
	Conditionalities of EU funding instruments	Instruments such as the JTM, RRF, and ESF+ introduce specific requirements related to timelines, co-financing, and administrative procedures. These conditions influence which actors are able to access funding and how interventions are implemented.

The inequality dynamics observed in Western Macedonia are rooted in a set of structural conditions that define the baseline within which policies operate.

The most significant of these is the region's long-standing dependence on lignite. For several decades, lignite-based activities accounted for a substantial share of regional employment and income. The accelerated phase-out has therefore generated a structural adjustment of considerable magnitude, with estimates indicating that approximately 15,000 to 20,000 jobs may be directly and indirectly affected (Christiaensen and Ferré, 2020; European Commission, 2022). In a context of **limited sectoral diversification**, the regional economy faces constraints in absorbing displaced labour and maintaining income levels.

The **structure of new investments** further shapes these dynamics. The transition is characterised by a concentration of capital in large-scale renewable energy projects. While these investments are central to achieving decarbonisation targets, they are typically capital-intensive and associated with lower long-term employment intensity compared to lignite-based activities (Kaldellis et al., 2025). In addition, their reliance on external firms and supply chains may limit the extent of local economic spillovers.

Labour market characteristics represent an additional structural factor. The workforce is largely composed of workers whose skills are closely linked to lignite-based activities. Available evidence indicates that a significant share of workers lacks foundational digital competencies, while the overall educational profile remains skewed towards lower and medium qualification levels. For example, data from the Public Employment Service (DYPA) show that more than two-thirds of unemployed individuals have primary or secondary education, while less than 1% hold postgraduate or doctoral qualifications. These structural characteristics are directly reflected in the design and uptake of labour market interventions, such as ESF+ training voucher schemes implemented by the Public Employment Service (DYPA), which aim to support reskilling but operate within these existing constraints.

Demographic trends reinforce these constraints. Population decline - estimated at over 10% between 2011 and 2021 - combined with sustained youth out-migration, reduces the availability of skilled labour and weakens the region's innovation capacity (ELSTAT, 2022; Stergiou et al., 2024). At the same time, **spatial differences** in exposure to transition-related investments shape local perceptions, with areas experiencing limited visible benefits expressing more negative expectations regarding economic prospects (Spanidis et al., 2025).

Institutional conditions also contribute to shaping outcomes. The transition is largely coordinated at the national level, with regional actors operating within predefined

frameworks. While this facilitates coordination and policy coherence, it also influences the extent to which local knowledge and priorities are incorporated into decision-making processes (Lypiridi, 2021).

Finally, **technological readiness** varies significantly across firms. The adoption of digital technologies requires a baseline level of absorptive capacity, including access to skills, finance, and organisational capabilities. Firms with higher initial capacity are therefore more likely to benefit from digital innovation policies, while others participate more gradually.

Taken together, these structural drivers define the context within which policy mechanisms operate.

3.3 Cross-Cutting inequalities and contextual constraints

In addition to structural conditions, the transition generates a set of cross-cutting pressures that influence how policies are experienced across social groups.

One of the most immediate concerns relates to **energy poverty**. The transition disrupts district heating systems historically powered by lignite, creating short- to medium-term uncertainty in energy provision. Evidence indicates that these changes may disproportionately affect vulnerable groups, including low-income households and specific demographic groups such as women (Andreosatou, 2024). While alternative systems are being developed, transitional gaps remain relevant in shaping short-term distributional effects.

Moreover, transition policies often assume that displaced workers can move into new sectors through reskilling. However, empirical evidence suggests that this process is uneven. The skills gap is not limited to technical knowledge but includes differences in educational background, work experience, and digital literacy. At the same time, the employment intensity of renewable energy systems is lower than that of lignite-based activities, which affects the overall capacity of new sectors to absorb labour.

Available assessments indicate that a substantial proportion of workers - estimated at up to 50% - require reskilling, particularly in relation to digital and technical competencies. However, participation in lifelong learning remains low (around 3–4%), which influences the pace at which workforce adaptation can occur. This combination of factors shapes the trajectory of labour market adjustment.

These cross-cutting pressures do not operate independently but interact with structural conditions, influencing how policy interventions translate into outcomes.

3.4 Policy mix in practice: mechanisms across the policy process

The effects of the transition on inequalities are shaped by how the policy mix operates in practice across design, implementation, and monitoring stages.

At the design stage, the policy mix combines infrastructure investment, digital innovation, and labour market interventions. While this reflects a comprehensive approach, **green and digital policies are often developed in parallel rather than as fully integrated components**

of a unified strategy. This influences the extent to which synergies between transitions are realised.

The structure of policy instruments also shapes access conditions. The **complexity of funding mechanisms** and the requirements associated with large-scale projects influence which actors are able to participate. Actors with higher administrative capacity and access to financial resources are generally more able to combine funding sources and engage with multiple programmes.

During implementation, these differences become more visible. Evidence from stakeholder consultations indicates that access to funding varies across actors, with SMEs facing administrative and financial constraints. Digital innovation initiatives provide targeted support, but their uptake depends on the existing capabilities of firms. Similarly, ESF+ training voucher schemes implemented through DYPA are not always closely aligned with the specific skill requirements associated with emerging investments in renewable energy and digital technologies, which influences their effectiveness in facilitating labour market transitions.

At the monitoring stage, the policy framework includes a wide range of indicators tracking implementation progress. These indicators primarily capture inputs and outputs, such as funding allocation and participation rates. However, there is more limited **monitoring of distributional outcomes**, including employment quality, income dynamics, and access to opportunities across different groups and territories. This influences the extent to which emerging inequalities are systematically identified within the policy process.

Across these stages, differences in access, capacity, and alignment contribute to differentiated participation patterns.

3.5 Interaction effects between green and digital transitions

The interaction between green and digital transitions introduces additional dynamics that shape inequality outcomes. One key dimension is the emergence of **combined skill requirements**. Many new roles require both technical and digital competencies, increasing the complexity of labour market transitions. This affects workers differently depending on their existing skill profiles and access to training opportunities.

At the same time, digitalisation tends to develop more rapidly in firms and locations with **higher initial capacities**. This can contribute to spatial and economic differentiation, as firms with greater resources and capabilities are more able to adopt advanced technologies and participate in innovation programmes.

However, digitalisation also introduces **opportunities for mitigating inequalities**, for example by enabling new forms of economic activity or improving access to services. The extent to which these opportunities are realised depends on how digital policies are implemented and how accessible they are to a broad range of actors.

3.6 From policy assumptions to uneven outcomes

The analysis highlights a gap between policy assumptions and observed outcomes. While policies assume that investment, reskilling, and digitalisation will support inclusive growth, their effects are mediated by structural conditions and implementation dynamics.

As a result, participation in the transition varies across actors and territories. Economic opportunities tend to be more accessible to actors with higher initial capacity, while others engage under more constrained conditions. Labour market adjustment remains uneven, and spatial differences in access to opportunities persist.

At the same time, the transition has achieved measurable progress. Significant financial resources have been mobilised, decarbonisation targets are being advanced, and institutional structures such as the Just Transition Observatory and the SYNERGiNN EDIH have been established. These developments provide a basis for further policy refinement.

Overall, the outcomes of the transition are shaped by the interaction between policy design, implementation mechanisms, and regional conditions. Strengthening alignment across these dimensions remains central to improving distributional outcomes.

Access to policy instruments is influenced by administrative and financial capacity, affecting the ability of different actors to participate. Labour market adjustment is shaped by the interaction between skill requirements and workforce characteristics. Economic opportunities are distributed unevenly across space, reflecting differences in investment patterns and local conditions. Finally, variations in absorptive capacity influence how firms engage with digital transformation. These mechanisms operate simultaneously and interact with each other, producing cumulative effects that shape the overall distributional outcomes of the transition.

Greece | Twin Transition

Figure 7 Summary table on Greece’s twin transition

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4 Conclusions

The Region of Western Macedonia occupies a critical position within Europe's climate transition agenda, functioning as a high-stakes testing ground for the socio-economic viability of the twin green and digital transition. The Greek government's commitment to the rapid phase-out of lignite by 2028 constitutes a necessary response to European climate objectives and aligns with the broader ambitions of the European Green Deal. In support of this transformation, a comprehensive policy architecture has been mobilised, combining substantial financial resources from the Just Transition Fund and the Recovery and Resilience Facility with targeted initiatives to strengthen digital capacity, including the establishment of the SYNERGiNN European Digital Innovation Hub.

The analysis presented in this report, however, demonstrates that the current trajectory of the transition is shaped by deeply embedded inequalities that permeate all stages of the policy cycle. The transition is unfolding under significant temporal pressure and within a predominantly centralised governance framework, which limits the incorporation of place-based knowledge and reduces the effective participation of local actors. As a result, the policy mix—despite its scale and ambition—tends to favour actors with pre-existing administrative capacity, financial resources, and technological readiness, including large energy firms and institutional stakeholders. In contrast, the groups most exposed to the structural impacts of the transition, notably displaced workers and small local enterprises, face multiple and reinforcing barriers. These include pronounced skills mismatches, limited digital capabilities, and restricted access to complex funding mechanisms, often described by local stakeholders as a “technical race”.

If these dynamics persist, there is a tangible risk that the transition will not lead to inclusive regional restructuring but instead to the emergence of a new form of economic concentration, in which the benefits of green and digital investments accrue unevenly. In this sense, the transition risks replacing a carbon-intensive monoculture with a more technologically advanced but equally exclusionary development model.

Addressing these challenges requires a recalibration of policy priorities and governance arrangements. First, there is a clear need to strengthen the place-based dimension of the transition. While national coordination remains essential, greater decision-making capacity should be devolved to regional and local actors to ensure that investments reflect territorial specificities and local socio-economic conditions. Second, labour market policies must move beyond generic training provision towards more targeted and demand-driven approaches. This implies a closer alignment between reskilling programmes and actual employment opportunities, as well as a stronger emphasis on foundational digital skills to address the structural barriers faced by large segments of the workforce.

In parallel, improving access to both green and digital transition opportunities is essential. Simplifying administrative procedures and reducing entry barriers for small firms would enhance the inclusiveness of funding instruments, while greater support for decentralised and community-based energy models could enable local actors to capture a larger share of the economic value generated by renewable energy investments. Furthermore, the social dimension of the transition requires more explicit attention. In particular, the risks associated

with energy poverty-especially in the context of the disruption of lignite-based heating systems-necessitate the integration of targeted and adequately funded support measures within the broader transition framework.

Finally, the monitoring and evaluation system must evolve to better capture distributional outcomes. While existing frameworks provide extensive data on financial inputs and activity levels, they remain limited in their ability to assess who benefits from the transition and under what conditions. Incorporating disaggregated indicators related to employment outcomes, income changes, access to funding, and participation across different social groups would enhance the capacity of policymakers to identify emerging inequalities and adjust interventions accordingly.

Taken together, these findings highlight that the success of the twin transition in Western Macedonia cannot be assessed solely in terms of decarbonisation progress or investment mobilisation. Rather, it depends on the extent to which policies are able to address structural inequalities, ensure broad-based participation, and distribute the benefits of transformation in a more balanced manner. In this sense, the region provides not only a test case for climate policy implementation, but also a critical lens through which the social and territorial dimensions of Europe's twin transition can be better understood.

5 References

No	Description/Link
R1	European Commission. (2025). Greece – Final updated National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP) 2021-2030 (submitted 2025)
R2	European Commission. (2024). EU Eco-Innovation Index 2024.
R3	European Commission. (2024). European Semester 2024: Country Reports
R4	European Commission. (2022). Just Development Transition Programme 2021–2027 (Greece).
R5	European Commission. (2022). EU Cohesion Policy: €1.63 billion for a just climate and energy transition in Greece.
R6	European Commission. (2021). EU Transition Performance Index 2021 – Interactive Report.
R7	European Commission. (2020). Greece – Final National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP) 2021-2030
R8	European Commission. (n.d.). Digital Decade DESI visualisation tool – DESI indicators (datasets & charts).
R9	Greece 2.0. (2021). Greece 2.0 – Recovery and Resilience Plan (English version)
R10	Ministry of Environment and Energy / SDAM (Special Coordination Authority for Just Transition). (2020). Just Transition Development Plan of Lignite Areas – Master Plan (Public Consultation, EN).
R11	Hellenic Statistical Authority (ELSTAT). (2023). Census Results (Population-Housing Census 2021) – Results publication (PDF)
R12	Eurostat. (n.d.). Unemployment statistics at regional level (Statistics Explained)
R13	Just Transition Observatory. (2023). Indicator System and Digital Monitoring Platform
R14	eJust4Skills. (2025). Sectoral reports 003.
R15	Greece in Figures. (2025). Brain Drain – Greece in Figures
R16	Kaldellis, J. K., et al. (2025). The impact of the green energy transition at the local level: How just is the fast implementation of decarbonization policy in West Macedonia? <i>Frontiers in Environmental Science</i> .
R17	Kollatou, T., Krestou, A., Tsiमितros, D., Stimoniaris, D., Maropoulos, S., & Kyriakopoulos, K. (2025, December). Policy, Regulation, and Financing in the Transition to Renewable Energy: A Case Study from Western Macedonia. In <i>Proceedings</i> (Vol. 134, No. 1, p. 4). MDPI
R18	Spanidis, P.-M., et al. (2025). Energy Transition in Greece: A Regional and National Media Analysis.
R19	Stergiou, K., Filippidis, K., Papoutzis, L., & Zourka, S. (2024). Transformative Dynamics of Youth Involvement in the Just Transition Process: The Case of Active Youths in the Region of Western Macedonia, Greece. <i>Archives of Business Research</i> , 12(1), 9-19.
R20	SYNERGINN EDIH. (2024). <i>The Digital Innovation Hub of Western Macedonia</i> .
R21	Kotzamanis, V. (2023). Brain drain stin Ellada: Anaptyxiakes kai demographikes proektaseis. In B. Kotzamanis (ed.)
R22	SEED CoVEs. (2023). Skills Analysis Report.
R23	Lypiridi, D. (2021). Just Transition Mechanism and Lignite Phase-Out in Greece (HAPSc Working Paper)
R24	The Green Tank. (2021). The course of Just Transition in Western Macedonia - Digital Consultation Workshops: Conclusions and Recommendations.
R25	Lypiridi, D. (2021). Just Transition Mechanism and Lignite Phase-Out in Greece.
R26	Ziouzios, D., Karlopoulos, E., Fragkos, P., & Vrontisi, Z. (2021). Challenges and Opportunities of Coal Phase-Out in Western Macedonia. <i>Climate</i> , 9(7), 115.
R27	Carley, S., & Konisky, D. M. (2020). The justice and equity implications of the clean energy transition. <i>Nature Energy</i> , 5(8), 569–577.

R28	Christiaensen, L., & Ferré, C. (2020). Just Coal Transition in Western Macedonia, Greece: Insights from the Labor Market. World Bank.
R29	Soja, E. W. (2010). <i>Seeking Spatial Justice</i> . University of Minnesota Press.

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